

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B100
 Date: 07 Jun 2005
 Take Off: 09:39:00
 Landing: 14:32:45
 Flight Time: 4h53m45

Campaign: CIRRUS
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: SW Approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsey Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
7	CCM2/Cld Phys Training	Jim Crawford	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry/TDLAS	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
9	Noise	Colin Hankinson	NERC
10	CCN/CVI	Paul James	FAAM
11	CCN Training / AMS	James Allen	University of Manchester
11	Observer	Alison Perry	FAAM
12	NOxy	Andy MacDonald	UEA
13	PTr-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
14	WAS	Jim Hopkins	York
15	ADA/CPI	Martin Gallagher	University of Manchester
16	CVI Training	Stuart Heath	FAAM
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B100
 Date: 7/6/05
 Project: CIRRUS
 Location: SW Approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
092346		engine start	-.30 kft	127	
092647		power change	-.30 kft	127	
092707		inu to nav	-.30 kft	127	
092918		taxy	-.30 kft	128	start
093900		T/O	-.28 kft	031	from cranfield
094200		asp open	5.0 kft	266	
101111	103126	Profile 1	10.0 - 28.0 kft	231	
102922		Profile 1	26.7 kft	240	rate of climb droppin
103139	104140	Run 1	28.1 kft	241	
104327	104753	Profile 2	28.1 - 30.0 kft	348	
105107	110109	Run 2	30.0 kft	081	
105641		Run 2	30.0 kft	084	intermittent contrail ing
110120	110611	Profile 3	30.0 - 32.0 kft	084	
110902	111857	Run 3	32.0 kft	299	
111857	112154	Profile 4	32.0 - 33.0 kft	294	
112107		Profile 4	32.8 kft	265	proper contrails!
NO RUN 4					
112454	113457	Run 5	33.1 - 33.0 kft	084	
113513	113707	Profile 5	33.2 - 34.0 kft	088	
114347	120545	Run 6	34.0 kft	277	
120821	122721	Run 7	32.1 - 32.0 kft	076	
122457		Run 7	32.0 kft	080	contrails stopped
123139	124241	Run 8	30.0 - 30.1 kft	270	
124652	125644	Run 9	28.1 - 28.0 kft	080	
125859	131025	Run 10	27.1 kft	276	
131302	132256	Run 11	25.0 - 25.1 kft	091	
132505	133655	Run 12	23.0 kft	265	
133852	134854	Run 13	22.0 kft	096	
141635		asp closed	7.2 kft	063	
143245		Land	-.29 kft	033	cranfield
143754		standstill	-.28 kft	307	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B100 Track 07-JUN-05

Sortie Brief UTLS CIRRUS 4 (Cirrus cloud microphysics and chemistry Option 1)

Flight Number B100

Date 7th June 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To make measurements of the microphysics of cirrus clouds and of their interaction with local aerosol and oxides of nitrogen. To investigate the effects of precipitation from the cloud on the vertical distribution of aerosol and oxidized nitrogen

Sortie Location: SW approaches/ SW Bristol Channel in layers of cirrus

Sortie Summary: The aircraft will initially make a vertical profile from well below cloud base to above the top of the cirrus. It will then make a series of straight and level runs of 10 minutes duration at several altitudes below, in and, when possible, above the cloud top. The straight and level runs above and below cloud will concentrate on determining the gaseous composition and aerosol physical and chemical properties of the air. Measurements of the vertical wind velocity will be made here. A straight and level run will be made very close to cloud base to determine whether supercooled water droplets or ice crystals are being activated.. Runs progressively deeper into the cloud will then be flown. SLRs will also be made in the fall streaks of the cirrus to characterise the precipitation in this region and to investigate the influence of the evaporation of the precipitation on the aerosol properties and trace gases in the region of the fall streaks. Advantage will also be taken to fly in and make measurements of any aircraft contrails (and fall streaks from contrails) found in the region following (same approach as for the naturally Ci) .

Sortie Detail

- a. T+0 Take off and climb to FL120 for transit to operating area (with appropriate time [~20mins] - spent at FL100 for NO_x calibration)
- b. T+40 Perform vertical profile ascent P1 through cirrus from below cloud base to aircraft ceiling, or to above cirrus top whichever is the lower (at 1000ft/min).
- c. T+60 Descend (not profile descent) to below base of cirrus generating cells and perform straight and level run (SLR) parallel to the mean wind direction 300 feet below cloud base for 10 minutes.
- d. T+75 Turn through 180 degrees. Ascend to cloud base and perform straight and level run for 10 minutes just in cloud at the base of the generating cells. Deviations from the straight run may be made in order to penetrate generating cells provided such penetrations can be achieved with wings level.
- e. T+90 Turn through 180 degrees ascend to middle of cloud and perform SLR for 10 min
- f. T+105 Turn through 180 degrees and if possible ascend to above cloud top and perform straight and level run duration 10 minutes above cloud top
- g. T+120 Descend to below cirrus base and make level runs through fall streaks adjusting flight path to pass through fall streaks as required.
- h. T+135 Descend to lowest altitude reached by fall streaks and make and level runs through the residue.
(NB order of SLRs c-h may be changed by mission scientist to h-c if considered appropriate)
- i. Repeat items b to h as time permits (including profile P2 to above P1 ceiling if failed to get above cloud top in P1)
- j. T+260 return transit (with appropriate time spent at appropriate altitude for NO_x cal)
- k. T+300 Land

Sortie Title UTLS Cirrus 4 (Cirrus cloud microphysics and chemistry Option 1)

Scientific Aims:

1. To measure the total number of Condensation Nuclei (CN), CCN, IN* and the size distribution of optically active particles in clean and polluted air in the UTLS region over the UK. Assessment of their spatial distribution and their likely source based on tracer measurements and air mass history.
2. To quantify the extent to which air mass history, and gas and particle loading can affect the microphysical properties of cirrus clouds in the UTLS region, in particular, the size distribution, phase and morphology of cloud particles.
3. To obtain estimates of HNO₃ loss to cirrus clouds and the subsequent effect on the aerosol population after the cloud has evaporated using case studies involving one or more wave clouds.
4. To make observations of the number, size distribution, phase and morphology of droplets and crystals in cirrus cloud and the number and size distribution of interstitial particles and correlate these with measurements of tracers that identify anthropogenic influence. Hence building on objective 3 to investigate the influence of cirrus on the distribution of aerosol and gases in the UTLS region as cloud and precipitation evaporate.
5. To make an assessment of the chemical composition of the particulate in the UTLS region as a function of their size, their spatial variability and the effect different sources have on their composition.
6. To use measurements of the masses of key components as a function of size of cirrus particle dry residues and interstitial particles to determine if there are distinct chemical differences between activated and unactivated particles.
7. To establish the partitioning of oxidised nitrogen between the gas and aerosol phases as a function of air mass history and source region

Weather conditions

Cirrus cloud preferably associated with the polar front jet preferably over the UK.

Key Measurements

All instruments to be operated continuously.

1) Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID-1 and SID-2*. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits etc.
- ADA/CPI – as above
- CCN - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample per run, if possible.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.
- TWC – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.

2) FWVS – Switch off the lamp when frost point rises above -15C. Calibration should be performed following altitude changes.

3) WAS - 2 bottle samples per 10min flight leg unless otherwise notified by the Mission Scientist.

- 4) AMS - to be operated on Rosemount inlet. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight.
- 5) Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rear. Flight manager or Flight Scientists should monitor rearward video and inform Mission Scientist of any occurrences of contrail formation (or cessation) and these should be noted in log sheets.

B100 Crew:

- 1) Pilot 1 - Alan Roberts
- 2) Pilot 2 - Ian Ramsay-Rae
- 3) CCM - Gaynor Ottoway
- 4) CCM2/Cloud Physics - Paul James
- 5) Mission Scientist - Keith Bower
- 6) Flight Manager - Steve Devereau
- 7) Cloud Physics Training - Jim Crawford
- 8) Core Chemistry/TDLAS - Alan Woolley
- 9) Noise - Colin Hankinson
- 10) CCN - Stuart Heath training James Allen
- 11) AMS - James Allan
- 12) ADA/CPI - Martin Gallagher
- 13) WAS –
- 14) CVI –
- 15) FWVS –
- 16) INC -

Mission Scientist's Log

MSc: KEITH BOWER

CIRRUS 4

Flight No **B.100**.....

Date **07/06/05**.....

Page **1** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Rolling - 10:29:55
					T/O 10:39:18
					10:49:00 \approx 09:48:44
	(10:42:15) Transit	FL50			
09:49:30	T	FL50		52.0/1.5W	S.54°/-12.24° 542mb 7ms/34°
09:49:40	climb	from FL50	266		↑ to FL100
09:51:00	climb	FL90	249	52.0/1.5W	0.76°/12.66° 10/359 717mb
9:52:10	Trans	FL100	248	51.9/1.9W	NOXY calcs start -1.2°C/-19.42°C 10m/s/356° 696mb @ 253kts
9:59:12	T	FL100	259	51.8/2.6	Cirrus ahead + contrails - over Severn bridge - Left 696mb -0.15°C/-16.65°C 8m/s/349° (248kts)
					SO ₂ OK ✓ Bulb replaced - Not seeing signal (250kts)
10:05:00	T	FL100	233	51.6/3.3W	Heading Change +0.21°/-21.21° 6m/s/337° 696mb
10:09:00	T	FL100	231	51.5/3.6W	SO ₂ 3ppb NOx -1.15ppb CO 123.1ppb
10:10:42	T	FL100			NOXY complete
10:11:10	PI st	FL100-240	251	51.3/3.6W	Climbs to FL240
10:12:52	PI				LTI annis on
10:15:08	PI				Photos 1-3
10:16:01	PI	14000'	236	51.2/4.2W	-7.02°/-31.24°C 5m/s/353° 264kts 585mb
10:12:15	PI	19820'	240	50.9/4.6W	layer ahead 18-20,000' H - layer above
10:22:48	PI	21600	240		is uniform 461mb -20.0°/-26.0° 8/314°
10:25:15	PI		240		Photos 2 R, L.
10:26:18	PI	FL240	240	50.7/5.3W	-28.88°/-40.33° 11/301 366mb 310kts
		FL260			Wherry Cloud Upward
10:29:18			240	50.6/5.5W	-34.32°/-44.0° 12m/s/305 358mb
					2D - perhaps SIDI / SAR LIR, ↑ conc.
10:30					

KNB B57
(=GMT+1:16)

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci K.N. BOWER

ORRUS 4

Flight No **B.100**.....

Date 07/06/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:31:25	end P1	FL 280			
10:31:37	start R1	FL 280			some egg-plats
	R1	FL 280			-36.59/-37.19°C Bm/s/311 CPI SIR/LIR 2DC-2DP-SID. stall-no turb.
10:33:22	R1	FL 280	240	50.4/6.1	R Facing Cam - Contrast 1000' ago 328mb
10:34:41		FL 280	240	50.3/6.3	Core Chem Calc - done - WAS Start 328mb
					Wing Vortices - R Camera - just above Mintra
10:37:01					level - pressure drop → nucleation
10:38:12			240	50.2/6.6	2D - 2DC - in/out CPI b/rossalt
10:41:40	end R1	FL 280		50.0/7.1	-38.13/-36.25°C 18 m/s/309 329mb 320 kts
					(with new lead N so that can carry out runs
					parallel to wind - with clouds - P absent
10:43:25	st P2	from FL 280	351	50.0/7.2	Start Profile
					2D - concs dropping CPI - BR.
					Out at 29000
					SID 2 - PC fallen out
10:47:43	end P2	FL 300			Above CT
10:49:20	SLR	FL 300	345	50.5/7.3	16/307° -45.66/-41.93
					Not Contracting Now - Blue every now and again
10:50:09					Contracts ahead / higher - Now turning Right
					2D - SID PC up and running.
10:51:06	st R2	FL 300	84	50.7/7.1	Above CT - Cloud ahead at this z
10:52:30					BR - CPT, 2DC - continues gap - now in
10:53:18	R2	FL 300	84	50.7/6.9	Out of Cloud again -44.02/-40.97 10 m/s/309
10:53:30	R2				Back in Cloud
10:58:52	R2	FL 300	84	50.7/6.0	PCASP - spikes - coincident with 2D

SIR profile BR - some large BR -43.9/-41.7
12 m/s/517° 300mb 351 kts

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci: K.N. BOWER

CIRUS 4

Flight No **B.100**.....

Date 07/06/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:01:08	end R2	FL 300			
11:01:17	st P3	FL 300	84	50.7/5.5V	CT looks much higher here (so can't see thro')
11:03:45					Photo? LMS/PCMS
					iD/b - ZPC ZDP out of range - SID down
11:06:11	end P3	FL 320	83	50.7/4.8W	-48.93/-47.4' 14ms/323 274ms 352kts 10/cm
					E-mail - Dave Kendra - 2hr left in C.!!
11:08:54	st R3	FL 320	294	50.9	-48.97/
11:10:20	R3	FL 320		50.9/4.9	-48.89/-47.74°C 21ms/310 274ms 349kts
					Someone landed on AMS k/a - last run.
11:13:15h	R3				New heading out above CT - still some
11:15:00	R3	FL 320	295	51.1/5.6	Back in cloud - 49.55/-47.27 23ms/306
					(next we will try and get up another 1000' - head back in a more easterly direction - A7C
11:17:00	R3	FL 320			Very near CT. require of plates - new more columns / plates / mix
11:17:58	R3	FL 320	295	51.2/5.9	SID2 fallen over again
11:18:53	(end R3 / start P4)		294	51.2/6.0	23ms/301° -49.75 -46.16
					CPC - behaving fine - then s
11:20:12	P4	32400	266	51.2/6.2	lots here plate / irregular plate - just at end R3
11:21:20		32800			2 Photos - top on Carbaid / C.
11:21:54	end P4	FL 330	266	51.2/6.4	CT - seems lower here in West. - Right Turn
11:23:40	turn	FL 330	↻	51.3/6.5	- Photo CT's during turn. CEN start
11:24:33					Cloud Patch. (prob during CEN summit)
11:24:54	st R5	FL 330	85	51.3/6.3	-52.34/-49.94 16ms/297° 261ms 343kts
11:27:40	R5	FL 330	90	51.3/5.4	2 Photos - of CT -52.2/-50.7° 14ms/304° 261ms

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci K.N. Bower

CIRUS 4

Flight No **B.100**.....

Date 07/06/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:33:04	RS	FL320	85	51.3/5.0	-52.14/-50.02 16m/s/309
					gone thro - some particles - small 50µm
					high peaks precip - some time.
					CCN - gone plng
11:34:57	end RS start PS		89	51.3/4.5	(Sudus. blobs small hex plate / proto BE) CPI
11:37:07	end PS	FL340	89	+51.3/4.3	-54.5/-52.06 250mb 14m/s/312 348hPa
11:38:00	-	FL340		51.3/4.1	still in CT. - changing heading (357hPa)
11:43:48	st R6	FL340	272	50.9/4.1	still in cloud -54.74/-52.21 20m/s/500 249hPa
11:46:41	R6	FL340	274	50.9/4.0	Above CT. - another layer above - pass not going to get above the high layer -
11:51:00	R6	FL340			Out of cloud now - none above - CCN start
11:51:50	R6	FL340	273	50.9/5.2W	-54.7/-53.15 14m/s/296 249mb 356hPa
11:54:55	R6	FL340			into cloud - above too
11:57:39	R6	FL340			above CT again / at CT
12:02:00	R6	FL340	272		Photo LMS - Above CT - + contrast - Photo R6S
12:05:27	R6 end		273	51.0	-54.9/-56.10 250mb 24/321°
12:05:46	R6 end		273	51.0, 71W	
12:07:00	descent				Photo at angle in RH turn of cloud
12:07:32	end des	FL320			
12:08:13	→ R7	FL320	76	(51.1/6.8)	
12:09:57	R7	FL320		51.1/6.8	11/315° -49.5°/-53.2° 273mb 347hPa
					2D
12:19:44	R7				Photo LMS - alt + Contrast.
12:25:16	R7	FL320	80	51.3/4.4W	Photo LMS of entire cloud depth -
12:27:05					(New cloud above, CCN spectrum den

FL 200 1
 FL 300 2
 FL 320 3
 FL 330 5
 FL 340 6

ED ⇒ CB
 FL280
 310
 320
 330
 L
 260 1hr
 250

33
 32
 31
 30
 29
 28
 27
 26

2hr
 1.5hr

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci: K.N. BOWER

CIRRUS 4

Flight No B.100.....

Date 07/06/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:27:19	end R7	FL320		51.3/4.0W	turning to W leg at FL300 -49.12/-47.34
12:29:49	descend				FL320 → FL300 (334kt)
12:31:51	end R8	FL300	271	51.1/4.4W	-44.36/-42.95 In Cloud 19m/s/320° 300mb
12:32:58	R8	FL300	270	51.1/4.6	out of CT again - CPI low conc 40µm pl 2DC - flat lining - no particles
12:34:44	R8				Core Chem Calc done → WAS
12:38:30	R8				Small Plates (30-80µm) Skeletal plate CPI - Trigonal + Round Hex Plates - counts assembled plates, 2DC - small mistle
12:40:39	R8	FL300	268	51.1/5.5W	-44.19°C/-42.75°C 17m/s/306° 300mb 333kt (with cloud (into wind) so got full 10mins on red leg)
12:41:43	R8	FL300			(In CT again - went thro' independently - will subside N on return leg to stay in cloud)
12:42:36	end R8	FL300		51.0/5.9W	turning - descend into cloud FL280 - descending
12:43:40	turn ↓				Photo in RH beam - CT + billows? NOX! ✓
12:45:10					Photo RHS Wide angle of full cloud depth portrait
12:46:31	R9 st.	FL280	81	51.3/5.8W	Photo LHS - A/C1 control
12:48:20					CPI - Photo ahead 12:48:50 2 photos RHS <small>wide portrait into approx</small>
12:50:15	R9	FL280	86	51.3/5.3W	-38.71/-37.27°C 15m/s/316° 328mb 317kt
12:50:51	R9	FL280	85	51.3/5.1	^{KP} In hole again - ^{yes} 2DV ✓ CPI still seeing ice
12:52:35	R9	FL280			^{KP} In cloud again 2DC ✓ CPI ✓
12:54:27	R9	FL280			Out of cloud again
12:55:15	R9	FL280	86	51.3/4.6	Photo RHS Low Cloud + plane + control
12:56:40	end R9	FL280		51.3/4.4	Going into cloud again

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci K. N. BOWER

CIRUS 4

Flight No **B.100**.....

Date 07/06/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:58:59	R10	FL270	272	51.4/4.4	19m/s/319° -36.35/-35.25° 343mb 312kt (deer in cloud - 2 more runs after this)
13:10:25	R10 end	FL270	89	51.5/5.8	-36.97/-35.47 345mb 13/284°
13:12:54	R11 st	FL250	91	51.2 /	-31.1 / -30.12°C 375mb 15m/s/305° 300kt CPI - 2030µm Spherulites orc large 200µm assemb (BR brackets during descent) SD ₂ - only below 15000 ft - need pump
13:18:26					3 photo LMS (contrast + a/c) RMS + ahead
13:19:15	R11	FL250	83	51.2/4.9	-32.12°C / -35.75°C 375mb 9m/s/301° 302kt Now picking up some CO - AMS - all OK - 3025 behaving - counts bigger than other 3025 ~ 1000's / vs 5x10 ³ cm ⁻² 2DE - very low is 50 lit ⁻¹ spike - 10 lit ⁻¹
13:22:55	R11 end	FL250	83	51.3/4.3	☉ ↓ 250
13:25:09	R12 st	FL230	268	51.2/4.3	-26.19°C / -34.87°C 408mb 12m/s/306° CPI - last run 11 - large vomiting large plates / assemb! then more spherulites + large plates sublimation - descent prior to that run
13:28:10h	R12	FL230			Photo RMS + LMS
13:32:10h					CPI → may have gone thru small fall streak
13:32:46	R12	FL230	267	51.1/5.2W	409mb -26.5 / -34.25 9m/s/291° 288kt
13:34:55	R12	FL230	267	51.1/5.5W	fall streaks ahead - extend run into them
13:36:55	R12 end	FL230	9	51.1/5.7W	missed the streaks
13:38:00	9 ↓				2 photo RMS in left beam - angle
13:38:50	R13	FL220	92	51.0/5.6W	427mb 310 -23.67°C / -28.06 8m/s/298°

FLIGHT NUMBER	B100	DATE:	7/6/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CIRRUS					

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	OK
All cylinders pressures are OK	OK
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	OK

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	52		
POST FLIGHT	45	130	

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.45	0.4	1.09	0.069	
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)		Pressure Cell (Torr)

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-1	-1
NO (ppbV)	-0.22	-0.15	0.08	-0.10	0.02	0.13	-0.04
NO ₂ (ppbV)	-0.62	-0.62	-0.62	-0.62	-0.76	-0.86	-0.68
NO _x (ppbV)	-0.84	-0.77	-0.70	-0.72	-0.74	-0.73	-0.75
SO ₂ (ppbV)	0.93	0.32	0.50	0.41	0.11	0.65	0.49

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

FLIGHT NUMBER	B100	DATE:	7/6/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CIRRUS					

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
11:40:09	340	74.31	91.59	6805.51	50	6.22	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.84	0.7	0.75	0.933	0.066	ALARM
12:10:31	210	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		74.45	90.34	6724.04	50	6.48	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
33.76	0.7	0.8	0.956	0.067	ALARM		
12:34:31	300	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		75.11	89.63	6732.21	50	6.73	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
33.79	0.7	0.75	0.984	0.067	ALARM		
12:49:41	280	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		75.54	88.89	6714.39	50	7.01	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
33.88	OK	OK	OK	OK	ALARM		
13:01:57	270	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		76.02	88.71	6743.48	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
33.82	OK	OK	OK	OK	ALARM		

FLIGHT NUMBER	B100	DATE:	7/6/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CIRRUS					

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

ASP opened 09:42

TO 9:38:37

TDLAS 10 s behind HORACE

11:55 TDLAS laptop switched itself off though data appears to be logging

FL250 non need for Co cal

FL 230 Quick cal performed

12:45 Co2 large increase

Leak on WAS case 2

ASP closed @ 14:15

CLLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

Page of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:17	Aux comp	2 fell	Over again	Autosave setup	For 1 min	intervals	failed				N.B. SID2 data files B100, B100a And B100b
	SID 2	ammeter	fluctauting	Between 0 & 2	Amps	Inst	Turned	off	11:26		
11:24:54	10	0.14	16	25	43	175	11	0	0	0	Run 5 @FL330
11:26:00	10	0.12	16	10	17	125	8	0	0	00	
11:28:00	11	0.28	16	25	7	200	8	0	0	0	
11:30:00	12.7	0.13	16	5	2.5	125	8	0	0	0	
11:32:00	10.8	0.12	17	25	14.5	100	11	0	0	0	
11:34:55	7	0.2	17	10	3	150	11				End of run and start P 5 FL330
11:37:03	14	0.2	17	25	9.5	125	11				FL340 end of P5
11:43:48	22	0.34	18	10	4.5	25	11				Start run 6 @FL340
11:45:00	7.64	0.24	18	85	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:47:00	16	0.14	18	10	10	100	11	0	0	0	
11:49:00	12.06	0.21	18	50	4	150	11	0	0	0	
11:51:00	9.5	0.09	18	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:53:00	13.9	0.22	18	100	45	100	11	0	0	0	
11:55:00	15.48	0.17	19	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:57:00	13.7	0.09	19	10	7.5	125	11	0	0	0	
11:59:00	44	0.55	19	75	8.5	100	11	0	0	0	
12:01:00	15.38	0.09	19	10	15.5	125	11	0	0	0	
12:03:00	14	0.09	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Left cloud bank behind
12:05:00	22.9	0.11	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:05:44	16.99	0.1	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 6
12:08:14	17	0.08	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 7 @ FL320
12:10:00	16.69	0.09	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:12:00	15.18	0.11	19	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	Accidental hit 28v sid1 switch
12:14:00	13.97	0.1	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Whilst reaching for comms
12:16:00	122	0.09	19	100	24	125	11	0	0	0	
12:18:00	19.1	0.11	19	75	28	100	11	0	0	0	
12:20:00	28.15	0.1	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:22:00	24.13	0.08	19	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:24:00	125	0.27	20	100	29	100	11	0	0	0	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:26:00	66	0.23	20	10	2.5	125	11	0	0	0	
12:27:00	30	0.09	20	10	21	175	11	0	0	0	End run 7
12:31:36	68	0.08	20	2	0.5	250	8	0	0	0	Start run 8 @ FL 300
12:33:00	46	0.09	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:35:00	32.17	0.08	20	7.5	14.5	150	10	0	0	0	
12:37:00	44	0.14	20	25	17.5	250	10	0	0	0	
12:39:00	55	0.08	20	25	9.5	200	10	0	0	0	
12:41:00	34.17	0.17	20	10	18	175	10	0	0	0	
12:42:37	18.09	0.09	21	0	15	225	10	0	0	0	End run 8
12:46:41	43	0.2	21	100	37	220	8	0	0	0	Start run 9 @ FL280
12:48:00	94	0.72	22	50	25	275	8	NOISE			
12:50:00	262	0.72	23	10	18	275	10	NOISE			
12:52:00	71	0.11	23	75	16	275	7	NOISE			
12:54:00	117	0.07	24	10	21	100	10	NOISE			
12:56:44	29	0.09	24	10	12	200	8	NOISE			End of run
12:58:57	23	0.1	24	10	5	250	8	NOISE			Start of run 10 @ FL270
13:00:00	99	0.14	25	100	25	225	8	NOISE			
13:02:00	30	0.18	25	50	14.5	175	10	NOISE			
13:04:00	219	0.08	25	75	20	200	10	NOISE			
13:06:00	40	0.16	25	90	32	225	10	NOISE			
13:08:00	298	0.35	26	90	40	225	10	NOISE			
13:10:26	37	0.08	26	2	0	0	0	NOISE			End of Run 10
13:12:55	34	0.2	26	75	31	200	10	NOISE			Start of Run 11 @ FL 250
13:14:00	37	0.17	26	100	24	225	8	NOISE			
13:16:00	63	0.17	27	75	2.5	425	10	NOISE			
13:18:00	33	0.09	27	10	5	225	8	NOISE			
13:20:00	201	0.12	27	75	26	350	10	1233	400	10	
13:22:55	33.17	0.11	27	2	3	200	8	8325	200	8	End of run 11
13:25:05	22	0.1	28	0	0	0	0	DEGRADED			Start of run 12 @ FL230
13:27:00	26	0.08	28	0	0	0	0	DEGRADED			
13:29:00	20	0.08	28	0	0	0	0	DEGRADED			
13:31:00	59	0.11	28	0	0	0	0	500	600	8	

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B100
Date: 07/06/2005

Campaign Name: CIRRUS
Operator: J. Hopkins (York)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
10:30:00			Take off; NOxy cals	
10:31:00			Level run at FL280 in cloud	
10:36:00	10:37:00	33	FL280, in cloud near top	2.32
10:39:29	10:40:29	34	FL280, in cloud near top	2.32
10:44:20			Profile 2 to FL300	
10:51:07			Level run at FL300	
10:52:48	10:53:48	35	FL300, still in cloud nearer top	2.18
10:58:35	10:59:35	36	FL300, still in cloud nearer top	2.18
11:02:20			Profile 3: FL300 to FL320	
11:08:55			Level run at FL320	
11:13:31	11:14:31	37	FL320 near top of cloud- patchy	2.02
11:16:30	11:17:30	38	FL320 near top of cloud- patchy	2.03
11:18:57			Profile 4: FL320 to FL330	
11:24:54			Level run at FL 330	
11:26:15	11:27:15	39	FL330 almost on top of cloud	1.93
11:32:01	11:33:01	40	FL330 almost on top of cloud	1.93
~11:35:00			Profile 5: FL220 to FL340	
11:43:47			Level run at FL340	
11:46	11:47:00	41	FL340 close to top of cloud	1.83
11:51:30	11:52:30	42	FL340 close to top of cloud	1.83
~12:06			Descend to FL320	
12:08:21			Level run 7 at FL320	
12:11:45	12:12:45	43	FL320 above cloud	1.98
12:17:21	12:18:21	44	FL320 within cloud	1.98
12:24:02	12:25:02	45	FL320 within cloud	1.98

~12:30			Descend FL320 to FL300	
12:31:39			Level run 8 at FL300	
12:36:01	12:37:01	46	FL300, bottle filled in hole in cloud	2.20
12:39:45	12:40:45	47	FL300, in cloud	2.14
~12:43			Descend FL300 to FL280	
12:46:52			Level run 9 at FL280	
12:51:46	12:52:46	48	FL280 in cloud (maybe in another hole in cloud though)	2.30
12:54:30	12:55:30	49	FL280 in cloud	2.30
~12:57			Descend FL280 to FL270	
12:58:59			Level run 10 at FL270	
13:03:26	13:04:26	50	FL270	
13:05:59	13:06:59	51	FL270	2.44
13:10:25			Descend FL270 to FL250	
13:13:02			Level run 11 at FL250	
13:15	13:16:00	52	FL250	2.56
13:20:30	13:21:30	53	FL250	2.52
~13:23			Descend FL250 to FL230	
13:25:05			Level run 12 at FL230	
13:29:30	13:30:30	54	FL230	2.40

Compressed air cylinder empty. p = 55 bar at start and during flight. Indicates possible leak on case 2?

CHECK RUN NUMBERS !!

R100 7/6/5

8:18 ~~0~~GMT

Tune

Resulted in 9% reduction

- not used

EM cal 2.475 kV
 3.62×10^6

Set up DMA

Sheath 4.06 μm
Sample 0.41 μm

IE cal

IE 2.422×10^6 AB 2.93×10^6
RJE NH₄ 3.753

AMS/PC 79.3, 90.5

New, old 1012/102

Time check - 45 seconds behind
HORACE

POST flight

EM 2.475 kV
 3.23×10^6

SMPS flows

4.0 0.41

QIE cal

IE 2.496×10^{-6}
NRIE 3.777

old/new 0.982 / 1.03

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B100

Date: 07/06/05

Instruments

1. Video – DFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off . Also, RFC (marked DFC...) is virtually black on pc monitor, whereas it displays well on video monitor unit.
2. Mission Scientist's laptop – needs new ethernet cable, the connector at the pc end is falling off.
3. Upper Pyrgeometer – Zero signal following radiance signal exactly.
4. NOX – occasional flutters above max chamber temp but otherwise okay.
5. Mechanical fault with Flight Manager drawer.
6. SID2 pc repeatedly crashed. Eventually switched off
7. Aft Core console pc drawer key bent badly – unusable.
8. WAS gas ran out prior to final fill.

Aircraft

Satcom H:- Two calls made by FM (both very brief)

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B100**

Date: 07/06/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	Y
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	N
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	Y
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	Y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	Y			

Untitled

00100 07-JUN-05 11:03:28 436 Hi Alan/Keith,

Hi Alan/Keith,

The Ci back edge is approaching you from the NW.
Best areas to work are probably: (a) 50 deg N, over Cornwall, or just over the sea going W (near Scillies). If possible, also head southwards. Or (b) Bristol Channel, as far up the estuary as you can realistically go (around Bristol ?). You probably have about another 2 hours max in either area on latest estimates from satpix. Is the Ci currently workable ?

Dave K (Exeter)

Flight B100 14:06:57

Heading 73 deg Speed 236 knots Height 11.0kft Press 669mb

Lat 51.7N Long 2.9W Wind 5 ms-1/ 334 deg

Temp -2.06C Dewpoint -20.41C

From start to now

Current values
 ○○○○ PRESSURE HEIGHT
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT

11.04 Kft
 50817 secs

● All
 C